

Visions, needs and requirements for Research Data and Practices

Key words: Research Practices, Trust, Data Quality, Reuse & Sharing

1. Demographic Survey

Note: This section is not collected during the interview. Rather, information is collected before the interview.

Scientific Domain/Discipline:

Institution:

Department:

Position/Career Stage:

Gender:

2. Introductory Questions

- What does your work focus on?
- What are the things that drive your work and why?

3. Data Handling

- What data are you working with?
 - E.g. primary data? Secondary data?
 - Numeric data, images, text, videos, audio, etc.
- How do you define/collect/preprocess/analyze/interpret/store data?
- What tools/software/services do you use for that? Why?
- Are you happy with how things are, or would different tools/software/services help you to be more efficient? If so, why are you not using them?
- What are the advantages/benefits of the tools/software/services you are using? What could be improved?

4. Trust in Data Quality

- What are the key steps in defining/collecting/analyzing/interpreting/storing data to know they are (and remain) high in quality?
- What constitutes the quality of high-quality research data (in your discipline), or rather what practices ensure quality in data?
- When and why do you have trust in the quality of your research data? When don't you?
- How do you judge the quality of research data of others/other disciplines, or rather, what are the criteria by which you judge it?
- When and why do you have trust in the quality of research data collected and shared by others?